

Bioengineering automation with winch enabled ATVs

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Abstract:

Winch enabled ATVs with level 2 or higher automation, are adopted to slope afforestation and bioengineering technologies to enable automation of DRR practices, with the use of slope binding and hydrodynamic engineering with Miyawaki Pockets, using runner plants, grasses and indigenous shallow and deep rooted trees.

Keywords: ATV, Winch Drive, Bioengineering, Miyawaki Pockets

What:

Miyawaki Pocket afforestation for altered hydrology towards DRR practices are described in Bheemaiah A. K. 2021 [1], an implementation with winch enabled ATVs, available in the Himalayan market is described as an accompanying paper to the above reference.

The remote driven Wyze car previously described by the author to have a hundred percent success at predicting landslides, Bheemaiah A. K. 2022 [2], can be used to model a winch enabled ATV for all terrain bioengineering and can demonstrate in a field setting a vast spectrum of surveying and ecological agroforestry and bioengineering roles. An ATV scales the Wyze Car in the planned bioengineering roles mentioned above.

How:

The use of scalable EV ATVs with winch attachments, lends itself to path planning on slopes towards small root ball size tree spade afforestation with the Mother of millions model of air layering.

Summary:

Main Points:

The mother of millions is a succulent plant with plantlets at leaf edges, we prove an implementation of a mother propagation plant with air rooting pods for air layering to an approximation to the mother of millions plant. Each plantlet is automatically or remotely planted with atvs equipped with three point hitch tree spades and the GPS coordinates of Voronoi lattice with a planting centroid of each cell.

2. Mother Divine , a new age spiritual organization creates several such spiritually significant mother trees for arboreal worship.

Applications:

Food Plot engineering, food forests and Miyawaki engineering, agroforestry, slope afforestation for disaster risk reduction, bioengineering.

Code Base: TBA.

Introduction.

Problem Definition.

The EV ATV is proven to implement path finding algorithms with level 4 automation, using a winch assist for elevations in excess of 60 degrees, for automated transplantation of air layered flora in all the layers of the planned Miyawaki pocket for bioengineering.

The UOL courses, UOL A 621, Miyawaki Landscaping[3] and UOL A 711, Analytical Rock Climbing,[4] include worksheets on path planning in robotics that include slope climbing path planning and Voronoi based automation of afforestation. In this paper we define a practical path planning approach to a winch assisted ATV with an analytical rope based follower technology for level 4 autonomy in an implementation of a Voronoi based landscape architecture blueprint.

Fig 1: The Mother of Millions Plant, an inspiration of mother plant based nursery propagation using air layering, the inspiration of

the syllogistic 'mother' of the Mother Divine abstractionism. Image webscrap source ¹

Air Layering Approach, The mother nursery tree. Inspired by the mahabodhi movement and the mother of millions or thousands of plants, is air layering technique to grow plantlets from branches to be pruned, leading to the pruning of branches with a root ball using off the shelf automated air layering technology.

Air rooting pots, rooting hormone and rooting media are used to automate air rooting and pruning, for 6 feet and taller transplantable, air rooted plants, for rapid Miyawaki creation as it uses a time complexity of one iteration for the air layering and the next for ATV based Voronoi afforestation. The level 5 plant group is the largest sized plant, and all other levels can be afforested with this technique.

Background.

Case Study

The botanical garden in IIT Mandi, is used as a study area for a planned slope reclamation project.

The messiah of peace, a scientist and druid, Akira Miyawaki was born in Hiroshima, a city devastated by a nuclear weapon, the city recovered its greenery in less than a century, proving the central hypothesis Formulated by Dr

Miyawaki, that in less than 5 centuries nature reclaims all land, to natural afforestation and we, as a force of nature, that very force, the taxonomy of which varies in Buddhist and neo pagan literature, can afforest degenerated land due to human activities.

Mandi is a university town in Kumaon district of the Pir Panjal range of the Himalayas with a high risk of landslides. Recent landslides have isolated the town, with a need for predictive analytics for logistic planning in an acceptance of natural disasters and bioengineering to mitigate effects of civil engineering and non natural hydrology. Land in Indian mythology is perceived to be of a neptunist origin, while increased development has rendered a bifurcation flatlanded scenario, with an active attempt by nature to resolve the engineering. Bioengineering helps nature, Bridge disruptions with natural technologies, both innovative and inherited to lower the risk of disasters. Slope afforestation with Miyawaki Pockets is one such measure, the botanical pathway, arboretum is the location of a proposed slope afforestation and hydrology experimental site, with a

Fig 2: An image of a hill facing the north campus of iit mandi, indicating exposed soil and rock substrate from developmental stress.

With the passage of time, such exposed surfaces, tend towards improper hydrology and related instabilities, leading to flash flood, mudslide and landslide combinations of slope instabilities

Miyawaki pocket of runner plants and edible fruits, in five levels.

The malus tree, found in the Indian himalayas with its affiliated plant group, is an indigenous plant used to afforest the slope, the hydrology and bioengineering role of this plant and its plant grouping is evaluated with a proposed afforestation schedule, with root ball depth and the needed plant acupuncture to symbiosis the root arbor.

Fig 2 indicates a geographical marker of a high risk area, by degradation of natural arbor cover, with human activities, and escalating remedial bioengineering techniques like Miyawaki Pockets.

We plan an ergodic path for the tethered winch rover, in a sequential rappelling mode for Voronoi based afforestation on levels 1 to 5.

In the next section we describe a leader follower algorithm, for automated rappelling based scanning of a Voronoi embedded in a GIS database.

If $[x]$ denotes the set of GPS coordinates, indexed by the level of the Miyawaki.

The linear spanning algorithm, denotes iterative leader based pivoting in one or more fixed points of anchorage of the winch line, and a rappelling based planting system, with a steering mechanism for precise points of afforestation.

We assume a human computer interaction with a path planning based on horizontal bouldering with remote terrain negotiation and a primary pivot and a horizontal pivoting for path planning.

Fig 3: Akira Miyawaki, a new age messiah of a restorative ecological movement. Image courtesy of YouTube.com

Conversion of 2D image to 3D Topography as GIS.

² Describes the use of Plex Earth 4 software from AutoCAD, for the above purpose.

Plex is an addon to AutoCAD Revit and other applications, for automatically importing GIS data from Google Earth maps.

Similar extension software for the Unity and Unreal engines for the creation of object files, GIS data and NFTs are available. A terrain map of the experimental locale mentioned in this paper with an NFT of the Miyawaki terrain is to be soon available.

ROI determination.

Segmentation of a ROI from an image for path planning, is achieved with several common segmentation algorithms. A filter to separate vegetation from the earth imagery is applied with a filter and a convolution mask.

The FPN seamless segmentation model is proven sufficient for the purpose of ROI determination and segmentation of exposed earth and rock elements with object categories of rock substratum and exposed soil, amenable to afforestation.

For the set of exposed soil substratum [s], we apply a map, [s] -> [v] for the generation of the

Voronoi layers v_i , for i in 1 to 5, in the GIS generated from the image to the GIS generator.

Path planning algorithms.

A survey of climbing algorithms and path planning.

The course UOL711, Analytical Rock Climbing, lists a comprehensive set of publications on path planning algorithms used by natural climbers and for robotics. We use a common bouldering leader follower Human In The Loop training algorithm ³for the Wyzer robot, with two tools, impact seeder and a three element tree spade.

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Proof of autonomous navigation with leader follower algorithms.

Provable Machine Learning, with PML or programmable UML⁴ architectures with executable plantUML, is a provable state based representation of the leader follower algorithm, proven to execute in correctness, without expensive testing.

With Human in the Loop training in simulations of path planning, the human leader can train the Wyzer robot to optimize a path efficiently, with proven machine learning.

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Discussion.

An implementation methodology for winch based autonomous ATVs are proven with provable machine learning to optimize planned slope afforestation using common bouldering algorithms with Human In The Loop training.

Future Work.

An experimental approach to path planning with the bouldering algorithms is planned on a standard climbing wall at an array of elevations, with the Wyze Car integrated with a 1:10 RC winch, with human in the loop training for path planning.

Miyawaki planning with Voronoi on GIS is to be computed, planned at Dee Mandala Farms in North Bangalore, India as a proven solution to a worksheet in the course UOL 621, Miyawaki Landscaping.

NFTs of Google Maps based terrain objects with vegetation objects will soon be available as a codebase on GitHub.

References.

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